

ISic4382

Epitaph erected by Sossis for his wife Rufina Marcia

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Recovered from demolition of a C19 house on via Quod Quaeris, Messina, and therefore presumed to come from the 'northern' necropolis

Coordinates

38.202117, 15.554338

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores, inventory ME 22800

Physical Description

A rectangular tablet of white marble (a small fragment on the middle lower margin has been reattached) with minor chipping to the upper and right edges. The rear is smooth.

Dimensions

Height 20 cm

Width 31 cm

Depth 3.6 cm

Layout

Five lines of Greek letters, unevenly set out and unevenly spaced (the first line is set apart by a larger gap from the remaining lines); a left margin is more or less observed.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate Greek letters, tending towards cursive in some cases, and reducing in size in the final lines. Moderately regularly and quite deeply incised with terminal serifs to the strokes. Alpha and Lambda extend the top of the right hasta. Alpha is closed lower left in the cursive style. Epsilon and sigma are lunate. Eta and pi have the same form (standard pi). Mu is cursive. Phi is significantly taller than other letters. Numerals are marked by supraline.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 17 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ῥουφείνα Μαρκία
2. ζήσασα ἔτη λε
3. Σόσσις ἀνήρ ἐπόη
4. σε ἰδίᾳ γυναικί εὐσεβεσ

5. τάτη μνημεῖον

Apparatus

Text after Zavettieri 2017 and photograph

Translation (en)

Rufina Marcia having lived for 35 years, her husband Sossis made this memorial for his own most pious wife

Translation (it)

Rufina Marcia vissuta anni 35, il marito Sossis fece alla propria moglie piissima un monumento

Commentary

Cf. ISic3521 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3521>] for another female member of the gens Marcia in Messina. The rare name Sossis is also attested at Catania in ISic1324 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1324>]

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Zavettieri, G. 2017. Le epigrafi. In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*. Palermo. pp. 167-171. At 169 no.5 fig.5

Licensed under a Creative Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4382. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381852>

archivio fotografico della soprintendenza di Messina

Photo courtesy of archivio fotografico della soprintendenza di Messina